

ABSTRACT
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Assessing the impact of sand fences on foredune development in high urban beach: A four-year study of Calafell Beach (Costa Daurada, Spain)

Carla Garcia-Lozano¹, Francesc Xavier Roig-Munar^{1,2}, Aron Marcos³, Josep Pintó¹

¹Universitat de Girona, Girona, Spain

²Coastal manager

³Councilor for Urban Ecology in Calafell City Council

Corresponding author: carla.garcia@udg.edu

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1 Introduction

Coastal dunes are dynamic ecosystems shaped by wind-transported sediments and human interventions. Historically, they have been managed to protect coastlines from erosion, but they have suffered significant degradation due to tourism and urbanization [1]. In this context, the study analyses geomorphological changes and management practices at Calafell beach (Costa Daurada, NE Spain) over four years. The beach stretches approximately 6 kilometers and is divided into two sections: Llevant Beach, located east of the port, and Ponent Beach, situated to the west. Calafell's economy is highly dependent on beach tourism, with its 27,000 permanent residents seeing their numbers triple during the summer, weekends, and holidays, reflecting the town's strong seasonal tourism influx.

2 Methodology

This study investigated the geomorphological changes of the foredune between 2020 and 2024 following the implementation of recovery-oriented management measures. The sand traps constructed in 2020 have dimensions of 10-15 meters in length, with a 50-60% porosity and a height of 70 cm, a width between 10 and 15 meters each, and orientated SSE. The study used digital elevation models (DEM) obtained from unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). UAV flights occurred in 2020 and in 2024, before and after the implementation of management measures. Analyses focused on sediment accumulation, including variations in dune height (Average height (AH), maximum height (maxH), and minimum height (minH)) and volume development (Vol).

3 Results and discussion

Llevant Beach has been the most positively impacted by the sand fences, with over 1,000 m³ of sediment accumulated (Figure 1), particularly in the wind retainer test field, which alone retained nearly 500 m³ over three years. This significant accumulation is mainly attributed to the presence of the test field and the protection provided by the port during Storm Nelson on March 27, 2024, which approached from the SSW direction.

Figure 1: Sediment gain in the foredune of Llevant Beach from 2020 to 2024.

In contrast, Ponent Beach (Figure 2) was directly exposed to the storm, leading to sediment deficits of approximately 500 m³ in some areas with sand fences. These same areas had shown positive sediment balances of 400 m³ the previous year, indicating that without the implementation of nature-based solutions, sediment loss in Llevant Beach would have been significantly higher.

Figure 2: Sediment loss in the foredune of Ponent Beach from 2020 to 2024.

References

- [1] Garcia-Lozano, C., Pintó, J., & Daunis-i-Estadella, P. (2018). Changes in coastal dune systems on the Catalan shoreline (Spain, NW Mediterranean Sea). Comparing dune landscapes between 1890 and 1960 with their current status. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 208, 235-247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2018.05.004>